

Towards AshGC, a graph neural network charge model for Open Force Field

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Abstract

Biomolecular force fields typically model electrostatic interactions with point partial charges assigned using expensive *ab initio* or semi-empirical approaches, which scale poorly to large molecules such as proteins. While protein force fields typically encode pre-computed charges for standard residues, this approach cannot account for non-standard components like covalently bound ligands or post-translational modifications and assigning charges to these systems remains a non-trivial task. Open Force Field has been developing a graph neural network-based method for efficient assignment of self-consistent charges to both small and large molecules for Open Force Field force fields. This charge model, called AshGC, has been fit to produce charges of semi-empirical quality at low cost. Here we describe the model, its architecture, featurization, training process, and release plan. AshGC is currently available as a release candidate under the name "openff-gnn-am1bcc-0.1.0-rc.3.pt" and can be used with Open Force Field infrastructure.

1. Introduction

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations have become essential tools in computational chemistry and biophysics research.¹ MD simulations have been used to investigate a variety of biological systems and phenomena, including conformational transitions,²⁻⁴ protein folding,⁵⁻⁷ membrane processes,⁸⁻¹⁰ and protein-ligand binding.¹¹⁻¹⁴

MD simulations use force fields to model potential energy surfaces as a function of atomic coordinates. Popular biomolecular force fields still largely follow the same, relatively simple, functional form first defined in 1969 by Levitt and Lifson.¹⁵ The potential energy is defined as the sum of bonded terms (bond stretching, angle bending, and torsional rotation) and nonbonded terms (van der Waals' and electrostatic interactions). Creating a force field typically involves fitting transferrable parameters empirically to experimental or quantum mechanical (QM) data, and these parameters can be applied generally to molecules within the scope of the force field.¹⁶

One common exception to this process is the electrostatics term, especially with small-molecule force fields. Force fields that are developed for particular groups of chemistry such as proteins, nucleic acids, or lipids, often do pre-compute or fit charges for standard residues and compounds within the parameter set. However, this approach is difficult to generalize outside of a small standard set. Instead, force fields traditionally fall back to a canonical charge model or method for deriving partial charges for arbitrary molecules.

Typically these charge methods involve fitting to QM properties, often the electrostatic potential (ESP) on a grid of points around a molecule; for example, one such approach (first published by Singh and Kollman)¹⁷ was used in AMBER ff84. However, this method suffered from several issues, such as a high degree of conformational dependence, poorly determined charges for buried atoms, and problems with modelling intramolecular interactions. The restrained electrostatic potential (RESP) method was developed to address these issues and remains widely used in force fields today, most commonly with HF/6-31G* as originally

published.^{18–20}

One difficulty with charge methods based on *ab initio* calculations is the computational expense, particularly if multiple calculations are needed to fit charges to multiple conformations. The AM1-BCC charge model was introduced as a more efficient alternative.^{21,22} Here, a semi-empirical AM1 calculation is performed to obtain population charges, which are then modified with bond charge corrections (BCCs) fit empirically to ESPs at HF/6-31G*.

AM1-BCC is the current canonical charge model used by Open Force Field (OpenFF) force fields. As the issue of conformer dependence remains a concern, where possible OpenFF uses the ELF10 method implemented by OpenEye’s `oequacpac` to generate charges averaged across an ensemble of up to 10 conformers selected to minimize strong electrostatic interactions between functional groups; this method results in much lower variance across possible charge sets.²³ However, where users cannot use this method (e.g. due to not holding an OpenEye license), the OpenFF infrastructure falls back to single-conformer AM1-BCC to balance accuracy with computational expense.

While OpenFF has published several force fields with the AM1-BCC charge model that perform well across varied tasks such as optimizing molecules in the gas phase,²⁴ generating conformational ensembles of macrocycles in the condensed phase,²⁵ or predicting protein-ligand binding free energies,^{14,26} two key issues remain. Firstly, the issue of conformer dependence is inherent to AM1-BCC and related approaches, as population charges or the ESP will differ depending on the molecular geometry. Recent work by Osato et al.²³ quantified the impact of charge variance due to the use of different conformers on free energy calculations and found that it could result in variation up to ± 5.3 kcal/mol in binding free energy results, or up to 6.9 kcal/mol in absolute hydration free energies. Secondly, QM and semi-empirical approaches scale poorly with molecular size, becoming prohibitively expensive for common simulation targets such as proteins.

Neural network models such as graph neural networks (GNNs) offer solutions that do not require QM calculations. GNNs are able to learn directly from data that can be encoded

as graphs, such as molecules, which can be transformed into a graph structure by encoding atoms as nodes and edges as vertices. Features can be chosen to exclude molecular geometry, ensuring that partial charges remain conformer-independent. In addition, GNNs scale efficiently; for example, Wang et al. developed a model, EspalomaCharge,²⁷ which was fit to AM1-BCC charges and runs with $\mathcal{O}(N)$ complexity. Here we describe our development of a neural-network based charge model building on top of Wang et al.’s work for assigning charges to both small and large molecules for the next generation of OpenFF force fields. We plan to release this model, which we call AshGC, as the canonical charge model of Sage 2.3.0, our next force field in the Sage line.

2. Model development

2.1 Charge dataset generation

SMILES were initially drawn from the following sources:

- the ChEMBL_eps_78 and ZINC_eps_78 datasets curated from ChEMBL and ZINC respectively by Bleiziffer et al.²⁸
- The Enamine Discovery Diversity Sets (DDS-10 and DDS-50, referred to as enamine-10240 and enamine-50240 respectively)
- The Open NCI Database dataset (Release 4 2012), initially downloaded from <https://cactus.nci.nih.gov/download/nci/index.html> (referred to as nci-250k)²⁹
- Components from the PDB ligand expo, initially downloaded from <http://ligand-expo.rcsb.org/dictionaries/Components-smiles-stereo-oe.smi>³⁰ (referred to as pdb)
- ChEMBL version 33 (released May 2023), initially downloaded from <https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/chembl/ChEMBLdb/latest/> (referred to as all-chembl)³¹

These datasets were additionally augmented by generating peptide chains up to 4 residues long, in a dataset referred to as **tetrapeptides**:

- For peptides ranging from 1 to 4 amino acids long, molecules were generated by combining single-digit amino acid codes of the 20 naturally-occurring amino acids into a FASTA, using combinations with replacement. Each molecule was added into the dataset without additional capping or modification.
- For each peptide chains ranging from 3-4 amino acids long in the previous step, the following modifications were made: an acetyl and N-methyl cap was added to the N- and C-termini respectively. In addition, all arginines were protonated and charged. Each of these modified chains was also added into the dataset.

2.1.1 Filtering for molecular size

We filtered the enamine-10240, enamine-50240, nci-250k, and pdb datasets to select for molecules comprised of elements in the set {H, C, N, O, F, P, S, Cl, Br, I} between 200–400 Da in molecular weight and up to 10 rotatable bonds. The ChEMBL_eps_78 and ZINC_eps_78 datasets were already filtered by Bleiziffer et al. ²⁸ to a subset of this criteria: they selected for molecules with the same elements, between 250–350 Da in molecular weight, and up to 7 rotatable bonds.

The ChEMBL dataset was filtered to select for small molecules from 1-199 Da, forming a new dataset referred to as **small-chembl**.

The additional **tetrapeptides** dataset was not filtered for size.

2.1.2 Enumerating protomers

Up to 2 protomers were enumerated for each molecule using the `OEGetReasonableProtomers` function in OpenEye’s `oequacpac`.

2.1.3 Conformer generation

For each dataset, conformers were generated for each molecule following a process that selects for conformationally diverse structures with minimal strong electrostatic interactions between functional groups as described below. Molecules for which conformers could not be generated were discarded.

- a pool of 1000 conformers was generated using OpenEye OMEGA^{32,33} via the OpenFF Toolkit. An RMSD cutoff of 0.05 Å was used, and a cis conformation was enforced on carboxylic acids.
- Up to 10 conformers were chosen from the lowest 2% pool using `oequacpac.OEELF`. The lowest 2% of the input conformers were selected as the intermediate electrostatically least-interacting set.

2.1.4 Charge generation

Single-conformer AM1-BCC charges were generated for each conformer and averaged to form AM1-BCC ELF10 charges. AmberTools charges were generated using the OpenFF Toolkit interface via its `AmberToolsToolkitWrapper` class. OpenEye charges were generated using the OpenFF Toolkit interface via its `OpenEyeToolkitWrapper` class. Molecules for which charges could not be generated were discarded.

2.1.5 Selecting for mid-size diverse molecules

We selected diverse molecules following a similar method to that laid out in Bleiziffer et al.²⁸

- The enamine-10240, enamine-50240, nci-250k, ChEMBL_eps_78, ZINC_eps_78, and pdb datasets were pooled together into an initial pool
- The environment of each atom in each molecule was labelled using the `GetHashedAtomPairFingerprintAsBitVect` function in RDKit with a `maxLength` of 2, 2048 bits, and 4 bits per entry.

- All molecules with atom environments that were represented less than five times across the entire dataset were selected
- For the remaining atom environments of the elements S, F, Cl, Br, I, P, O, N, and C, the four molecules with the highest number of as-yet unrepresented atom environments were selected. Atom environments were investigated in the order of the elements listed.

2.1.6 Data partitioning

These data were then partitioned into initial training and validation sets using an 80/20 split. A Morgan bit vector fingerprint was computed for each molecule with radius 3 and 2048 bits. A diverse initial training set (“`n04-training`”) was selected by Tanimoto distance using the RDKit MaxMin algorithm. The remainder of the molecules in the initial set were assigned to the validation set (“`n04-validation`”).

The `tetrapeptides` dataset was combined with `n04-training` to form an initial training set.

Finally, due to the size of the small-molecule ChEMBL `small-chembl` dataset, this dataset was partitioned into training and test components using a 70/30 split using the method detailed above. The training component was used separately from the initial set for additional fine-tuning.

The initial training dataset comprised 271204 molecules; the dataset composition is broken down in Table 1. The fine-tuning dataset comprised 39909 molecules from the `small-chembl` dataset.

2.2 Molecule featurization

Molecules were featurized using the OpenFF NAGL library. Molecules are first standardized (see section 2.2.1). They are encoded into graphs, where each atom was represented as a node with the following node features:

Table 1: Composition of initial training set

	# molecules
enamine-10240	6499
enamine-50240	35731
ChEMBL_eps_78	31185
ZINC_eps_78	78933
nci-250k	85322
pdb	10844
tetrapeptides	22690
Total	271204

- One-hot encoded element (values: C, O, H, N, S, F, Br, Cl, I, P)
- One-hot encoded atom degree (number of bonds, ignoring bond valency or type) of each atom (values: 1-6)
- The averaged formal charge over resonance forms for each atom (see section 2.2.2)
- Membership in rings of sizes 3, 4, 5, and 6

Bonds are encoded as featureless graph edges.

2.2.1 Molecular standardization

Molecules are standardized upon input into the NAGL AshGC charge model for both training and inference, applying a set of reactions to standardize the representation of a set of common functional groups and substructures. This standardization follows the same workflow as the MolStandardize³⁴ module of RDKit,³⁵ and uses the same standardization reactions.

2.2.2 Averaged formal charge

The averaged formal charge is the only molecule feature calculated in the NAGL library itself, instead of another cheminformatics backend. This follows a similar algorithm to that proposed by Gilson et al.:³⁶

- Hydrogens and uncharged sp³ carbons are temporarily removed from the molecular graph as they cannot be involved in charge transfer.
- Disjoint subgraphs are separated into individual fragments.
- For each subgraph that contains at least 1 electron donor and 1 electron acceptor, all possible electron-transfer paths are identified following the algorithm in Gilson et al. , and used to generate additional fragments with alternate resonance forms
- The average charge of an atom in these subgraphs is the averaged formal charge over all alternate resonance forms detected in the previous step
- The average charge of an atom not present in these subgraphs (i.e. an atom in subgraph that *does not* contain at least 1 electron donor and 1 electron acceptor, or a hydrogen or uncharged sp³ carbon removed in the first step) is the formal charge of that atom

2.3 Model architecture

Models were constructed and trained using the OpenFF NAGL library. Our model used the GraphSAGE architecture³⁷ as implemented in the Deep Graph Library (DGL)³⁸ to learn atom embeddings (GraphSAGE and OpenFF’s Sage line of force fields are otherwise unrelated). A molecule is transformed as a graph G whereby the atoms are represented as vertices and the bonds as edges. Each atom i is represented initially by the input features \mathbf{h}_i^0 .

For each round of message-passing k , the feature embeddings \mathbf{h}_j^k of all neighbouring nodes $j \in N(i)$ to an atom i are aggregated into a single embedding $\mathbf{h}_{N(i)}^{k+1}$:

$$\mathbf{h}_{N(i)}^{k+1} = \text{aggregate}(\{\mathbf{h}_j^k, \forall j \in N(i)\})$$

The aggregation function is selected to produce a permutation-invariant result, typically the sum or mean function; in this case we use the mean.

The aggregated neighbour embeddings are concatenated with the node’s embedding h_i^k during the node update, where σ is the activation function (in this case, ReLU):

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{k+1} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_v \cdot \text{concat}(\mathbf{h}_i^k, \mathbf{h}_{N(i)}^{k+1}))$$

The final atom embeddings are finally passed through a feed-forward neural network to predict three properties for each atom: an initial charge q_0 , the electronegativity e , and the hardness s . The electronegativity and hardness are used to compute a correction to the initial charge following a modified form of the charge equilibration scheme proposed by Gilson et al.³⁶ Where the approach in Gilson et al. derives each charge q_i for each atom i by minimizing the charge potential energy E

$$E = \sum_i (e_i q_i + \frac{1}{2} s_i q_i^2)$$

subject to the constraint that atomic charges sum to the total molecular charge Q :

$$\sum_i q_i = Q$$

We modify this approach to add a prior estimate of the charge $q_{0,i}$:

$$E = \sum_i (e_i q_i + \frac{1}{2} s_i (q_i - q_{0,i})^2)$$

which can be solved analytically using Lagrangian multipliers:

$$q_i = -e_i s_i^{-1} + q_{0,i} - s_i^{-1} \left(\frac{Q_0 - Q - \sum_i e_i s_i^{-1}}{\sum_i s_i^{-1}} \right)$$

where

$$Q_0 = \sum_i q_{0,i}$$

2.4 Model training

The model was trained using the Adam optimizer³⁹ to a multi-target loss function. In the first stage, it was trained to an initial training dataset for 500 epochs, before being additionally tuned to a second dataset of molecules under 200 Da molecular weight to improve performance for an additional 500 epochs.

The objective function was constructed as a weighted sum of the root-mean-square errors (RMSE) associated with charge, dipole, and electrostatic potential (ESP) targets.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \frac{1}{w_q} \mathcal{L}_q + \frac{1}{w_\mu} \mathcal{L}_\mu + \frac{1}{w_V} \mathcal{L}_V \quad (1)$$

\mathcal{L}_q is calculated as the element-wise RMSE between the predicted charge $q_{m,i}$ and reference AM1-BCC ELF10 charge $\hat{q}_{m,i}$ for the i th atom of molecule m in a dataset comprising N_{mol} molecules:

$$\mathcal{L}_q = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{mol}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{atoms}}(m)} [q_{m,i} - \hat{q}_{m,i}]^2}{\sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{mol}}} N_{\text{atoms}}(m)}} \quad (2)$$

where $N_{\text{atoms}}(m)$ is the number of atoms in molecule m .

Analogously, \mathcal{L}_μ compares dipole moments over each Cartesian component $j \in \{x, y, z\}$.

$$\mathcal{L}_\mu = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{mol}}} \sum_{c=1}^{N_{\text{conf}}(m)} \sum_{j \in \{x, y, z\}} [\mu_{c,j} - \hat{\mu}_{c,j}]^2}{3 \sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{mol}}} N_{\text{conf}}(m)}} \quad (3)$$

where $\mu_{c,j}$ is the Cartesian component of the dipole moment of conformer c of molecule m from the predicted charges \mathbf{q}_m , and $\hat{\mu}_{c,j}$ is the corresponding Cartesian component of the dipole moment computed from the reference AM1-BCC ELF10 charges $\hat{\mathbf{q}}_m$. $N_{\text{conf}}(m)$ is the number of conformers for molecule m .

In the first training phase, the ESP target \mathcal{L}_V also compared the RMSE between the ESP computed from predicted and reference charges at each grid point k :

$$\mathcal{L}_V = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{mol}}} \sum_{c=1}^{N_{\text{conf}}(m)} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{grid}}(c)} [V_{c,k} - \hat{V}_{c,k}]^2}{\sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{mol}}} \sum_{c=1}^{N_{\text{conf}}(m)} N_{\text{grid}}(c)}} \quad (4)$$

where $V_{c,k}$ is the electrostatic potential at grid point k for conformer c of molecule m projected by the predicted point charges; $\hat{V}_{c,k}$ is the electrostatic potential at grid point k for molecule m projected by the reference point charges; and $N_{\text{grid}}(c)$ is the total number of grid points surrounding conformer c .

In the fine-tuning stage, we updated the ESP target to calculate the ESP loss \mathcal{L}_V as the weighted RMSE to give more polarized regions higher weight:

$$\mathcal{L}_V = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{c=1}^{N_{\text{conf}}(m)} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{grid}}(c)} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{grid}}(c)} [|\hat{V}_{c,k}|(V_{c,k} - \hat{V}_{c,k})^2]}{\sum_{m=1}^{N_{\text{mol}}} \sum_{c=1}^{N_{\text{conf}}(m)} N_{\text{grid}}(c)}} \quad (5)$$

Across both training stages the charge weight $w_q = 0.02$ e, the dipole weight $w_\mu = 0.1$ e.Å, and the ESP weight $w_V = 0.001$ hartree/e.

2.5 Construction of a look-up table

In addition, we supplemented the neural network with a look-up table of AM1-BCC charges for molecules comprising up to three heavy atoms, as this is an area of chemistry where AshGC performs poorly.

Molecules were enumerated as follows:

- individual atom types were constructed by combining each element in the set H, C, N, O, F, P, S, Cl, Br, I with formal charges ranging from -4 to +4

- individual bond types were defined as single, double, triple, and aromatic bonds
- SMILES were constructed for pairs of atom types by combining them following the pattern "[at₁]bt₂[at₃]", where at₁ and at₃ are atom types and bt₂ is a bond type
- SMILES were constructed for triplets of atom types to create linear molecules following the pattern "[at₁]bt₂[at₃]bt₄[at₅]", where at₁, at₃, at₅ are atom types and bt₂ and bt₄ are bond types
- SMILES were constructed for triplets of atom types to create ring molecules following the pattern "[at₁]1bt₂[at₃]bt₄[at₅]bt₆1", where at₁, at₃, at₅ are atom types and bt₂, bt₄, bt₆ are bond types

Molecules that could not be parsed by the OpenEye or RDKit cheminformatics toolkits were discarded.

Charges were computed for each molecule with the OpenEye and AmberTools toolkits as described in section 2.1.4. Molecules for which charges could not be computed by either toolkit were discarded.

A final set of charges for the look-up table were obtained as follows:

- For molecules where OpenEye was able to assign AM1-BCC ELF10 charges, molecules were grouped by InChI to remove variance across resonance forms. A single set of charges for a unique molecule were derived by averaging all OpenEye AM1-BCC ELF10 charges for each InChI identifier.
- For molecules where OpenEye was unable to assign AM1-BCC ELF10 charges, molecules were grouped by InChI to remove variance across resonance forms. A single set of charges for a unique molecule were derived by averaging all AmberTools AM1-BCC charges for each InChI identifier.

When a molecule is passed to the AshGC model, its InChI is first checked in the look-up

table. If the molecule is present, the charges in the look-up table are returned. If not, the molecule is featurized and inference occurs as usual with the graph neural network model.

3. Model inference and usage

Model inference is carried out using the OpenFF NAGL library. Inference can occur through two pathways: through the DGL implementation of GraphSAGE, as was used in training, or optionally the re-implementation in OpenFF NAGL, which has only been validated for inference. The latter was created to provide a pathway for users to use the model without needing to install DGL.

The current AshGC release candidate is `openff-gnn-am1bcc-0.1.0-rc.3.pt`. This can be installed using OpenFF NAGL Models, and charges can be predicted either directly with OpenFF NAGL or through the OpenFF Toolkit.

4. Release plan

Open Force Field plans to release AshGC as a distinct charge model from AM1-BCC, which will necessitate an update to the SMIRNOFF specification⁴⁰ to add sections for graph neural network charges.

We plan to release a new force field, Sage 2.3.0, where all force field parameters have been re-fit using the AshGC charge model. This includes the van der Waals (vdW) terms, as previous work on electrostatics models has shown that improving electrostatics alone is insufficient to improve force field performance; re-fitting vdW parameters is also required.⁴¹ Sage 2.3.0 will also include further improvements to bonded parameters. It will be benchmarked on a number of benchmarks representative of common force field tasks: QM properties, physical properties (densities and enthalpies of mixing), solvation free energies, and finally protein-ligand binding free energies.

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